

Decoupling Africa: Foreign Aid and the Path to Native Economic Development

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ABSTRACT

This study examines whether foreign aid has supported or hindered Africa's long-term economic development by analyzing trends in Official Development Assistance (ODA), governance indicators, domestic resource mobilization, and macroeconomic performance across selected African countries.

The objective is to determine if aid has contributed to sustainable growth or reinforced dependency. A mixed-methods approach was applied, combining descriptive statistics, secondary macroeconomic data from the World Bank and the OECD (2004–2023), and a comparative analysis of variations in governance quality.

Findings show that while aid has short-term positive effects in countries with strong governance, it generally shows lower statistical significance than variables such as education, domestic savings, and women's economic participation. The analysis further reveals that high-aid countries often experience weakening domestic resource mobilization, policy dependence, and macroeconomic vulnerability.

The study concludes that Africa must transition from aid-dependence to indigenous development models by strengthening institutions, expanding intra-African trade, and building technological and innovation capacity. Recommendations include rethinking aid delivery, enhancing governance reforms, and prioritizing domestic resource mobilization to achieve sustainable economic self-reliance.

1. Introduction

For more than five decades, foreign aid has been a central pillar of Africa's development strategy. Large inflows of Official Development Assistance (ODA), concessional loans, and donor-funded programs were expected to accelerate economic growth, reduce poverty, and strengthen public institutions (see figure 1). However, despite receiving billions of dollars annually, African countries continue to struggle with weak economic structures, low industrialization, inadequate domestic resource mobilization, and persistent dependence on external assistance.¹ Recent global reductions in aid flows have exposed the fragility of these aid-dependent development models, compelling African nations to confront the sustainability of their economic trajectory.

At the same time, emerging cases such as Rwanda, Botswana, and Ethiopia demonstrate that internal reforms, good governance, and indigenous development strategies can yield stronger, more independent growth outcomes. This background provides the rationale for examining whether foreign aid contributes positively to Africa's economic development or reinforces structural dependency that undermines long-term progress.

2. Problem Statement

Despite decades of substantial foreign aid, Africa has not achieved the level of economic transformation expected from continuous external financing. Evidence shows that aid

inflows often correlate with weak domestic savings, limited industrial capacity, policy dependency, and vulnerability to external shocks. Regression analyses across multiple studies indicate that foreign aid is not a significant predictor of long-term economic growth, compared with variables such as education, women's economic empowerment, domestic savings, or birth rates.

This suggests that aid may not be addressing the fundamental drivers of development. Additionally, inconsistent governance quality across the continent results in aid producing positive effects in some countries while entrenching dependency in others. Therefore, the central problem investigated in this study is whether foreign aid promotes sustainable economic development or whether it perpetuates dependency and structural weaknesses in African economies.

This study aims to evaluate the long-term impact of foreign aid on African economic development and to determine whether African economies can achieve sustainable growth through indigenous, internally driven development models rather than continued reliance on external assistance.

3. Research Questions

- i. Does foreign aid significantly contribute to long-term economic growth in African countries?
- ii. What economic and governance factors influence the effectiveness of foreign aid?

¹ *Dambisa Moyo, Dead Aid: Why Aid Is Not Working and How There Is a Better Way for Africa, 1. American paperback ed (Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2010).*

- iii. Does foreign aid weaken domestic resource mobilization and institutional development?
- iv. Examine the relationship between Official Development Assistance (ODA) and key macroeconomic indicators of five African countries.
- v. Are countries with strong governance more likely to benefit from aid compared to countries with weak governance?
- vi. What indigenous development strategies have enabled some African nations to achieve self-reliance despite declining aid?
- vii.

“Decoupling Africa: Foreign Aid and Native Economic Development” challenges the prevailing aid-centric development model. The argument is that the long-term reliance on foreign aid has often created a cycle of dependency, distorted local economies, and stifled the growth of authentic, domestically driven development models² (see Figure 3).

The introduction of the concept of “decoupling” is not a call for the immediate cessation of all aid, but as a strategic imperative for African nations to progressively delink their economic destinies from the vagaries of international aid and, instead,

anchor their growth in the rich soil of their resources, ingenuity, and institutions.³

Figure 1: ODA Flows from all Donors by Region (constant 2014 US\$, billions)⁴

Literature on foreign aid to Africa is vast and deeply polarized. On one side of the debate, proponents argue that aid is vital for poverty reduction, infrastructure development, and human capital formation.⁵ Jeffrey Sachs has famously argued for a massive scaling-up of aid to help Africa escape the “poverty trap.”⁶

² Blessing Ernest, “Foreign Aid in Africa: Assessing Impact and Dependency,” African Leadership Magazine, February 28, 2024, <https://www.africanleadershipmagazine.co.uk/foreign-aid-in-africa-assessing-impact-and-dependency/>.

³ Pene Shako Lubunga, “Building up Indigenous Technological Capabilities in African Developing Countries,” *Technology in Society* 7, no. 1 (1985): 77–85, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-791X\(85\)90017-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-791X(85)90017-X).

⁴ Leonce Ndikumana and Lynda Pickburn, “The Future of Aid Effectiveness in Sub-Saharan Africa – A Research Agenda,” The Global Development Network’s Paper Series, *The Global Development Network*, August 2016, 12,

https://www.gdn.int/sites/default/files/Aid%20effectiveness%20paper%20of%20in%20al_2.pdf.

⁵ Katarina Juselius et al., “The Long-Run Impact of Foreign Aid in 36 African Countries: Insights from Multivariate Time Series Analysis*,” *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* 76, no. 2 (2014): 153–84, <https://doi.org/10.1111/obes.12012>.

⁶ Dr Kazi Abdur Rouf, Jeffrey Sachs, (2005). *The End of Poverty: Economic Possibilities For our Time*. New York: The Penguin Press. (Book Summary and BookReview), 2014.

The theoretical underpinnings of this view are often traced back to the Harrod-Domar model⁷, which suggests that aid is vital for poverty reduction, infrastructure development, and human capital formation.⁸ Jeffrey Sachs has famously argued for a massive scaling-up of aid to help Africa escape the “poverty trap.”⁹ The theoretical underpinnings of this view are often traced back to the Harrod-Domar model¹⁰, which suggests that aid can fill the financing gap between the investment required for growth and the domestic savings available to fund it.

Numerous studies on foreign aid and economic growth in the literature, particularly those related to Africa, suggest that foreign aid contributes to economic development.¹¹ Several authors have found a positive relationship between aid and economic growth; however, some studies emphasize that foreign aid can actually decelerate economic activities. Sound policies, institutions, and governance underpin studies that show aid has a positive effect.¹² A concise overview of research on foreign aid and growth is given by Mangir et al.,¹³ which includes information on the authors, independent variables, methodology, and findings.¹⁴

On the other side of the spectrum, a growing chorus of critics argues that aid has been largely ineffective, and in some cases, counterproductive. Dambisa Moyo’s “Dead Aid”¹⁵ is perhaps the most well-known critique, arguing that systematic aid has fostered dependency, corruption, and a rent-seeking culture among African elites. This view is supported by a body of research indicating that aid can undermine domestic institutions, distort local markets, and create a “Dutch disease” effect, in which large foreign-currency inflows appreciate the exchange rate and render exports less competitive.

For instance, the GDP growth rates in this African subregion (see Figure 2) suggest that low GDP growth is associated with high foreign aid inflows. In particular, this seems to hold for most of the study's periods, except for 2005–2006, 2011–2014, and 2016–2017. Except for 2015, when growth fell precipitously from 4.44% in 2014 to 2.48% in 2015, prospects are stronger from 2011 to 2017.¹⁶

⁷ HET, “History of Economic Thought,” accessed July 21, 2025, <https://www.hetwebsite.net/het/essays/growth/harrod/harrodgrowth.htm>.

⁸ Juselius et al., “The Long-Run Impact of Foreign Aid in 36 African Countries.”

⁹ Rouf, Jeffrey Sachs, (2005). *The End of Poverty: Economic Possibilities For our Time*. New York: The Penguin Press. (Book Summary and BookReview).

¹⁰ HET, “History of Economic Thought.”

¹¹ Girum Dagne, “Impact of Foreign Aid on Economic Growth of Ethiopia,” *The Indian Economic Journal*, ahead of print, February 6, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00194662231213583>.

¹² Sikiru Babalola and Waliu Shittu, “Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa: Examining the Roles of Institutions Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa: Examining the Roles of Institutions,” *International Economic Journal* 34 (June 2020), <https://doi.org/10.1080/10168737.2020.1780292>.

¹³ Mangir et al., *FOREIGN AID AND ECONOMIC GROWTH*, 113–114.

¹⁴ Mangir et al., *FOREIGN AID AND ECONOMIC GROWTH*, 112–114.

¹⁵ Moyo, *Dead Aid*.

¹⁶ Babalola and Shittu, “Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa.”

Figure 2: Foreign Aid (%GNI) and Economic Growth in West Africa¹⁷

The question of Africa's relationship with foreign aid reached a critical juncture in 2025, as traditional donor countries reduced their assistance and African nations faced mounting pressure to chart an independent path to prosperity.¹⁸ For decades, foreign aid has been positioned as the primary vehicle for African development, yet the continent continues to grapple with persistent poverty, economic vulnerability, and structural underdevelopment.^{19 20}

The recent global trend of aid reduction, exemplified by the United States' freezing of aid programs and European nations cutting their development budgets, has exposed the fundamental weakness of aid-dependent economic models. A significant decline is evident, dropping from \$64.8 billion in

2021 to \$60 billion in 2023, with U.S. aid falling further to \$12.7 billion in 2024.²¹ Apart from highlighting the weaknesses of aid-dependent economic models, this reduction has also created opportunities for African nations to develop alternative pathways to sustainable development.²² The current global reduction in aid flows presents challenges and unprecedented opportunities for African nations to accelerate their transition from aid dependency to indigenous development models.

Figure 3: ODA as a Percentage of Gross Domestic Capital Formation by Region²³

Africa's journey toward economic self-reliance is not merely a response to external pressures but a necessary evolution

¹⁷ Babalola and Shittu, "Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa," 4.

¹⁸ Muhammad Ali Pate and Phillippe Duneton, "Africa's Shift from Aid Dependency," *Think Global Health*, June 16, 2025, <https://www.thinkglobalhealth.org/article/africas-shift-aid-dependency>.

¹⁹ Ernest, "Foreign Aid in Africa."

²⁰ Rowland-George Omeni, "Africa's Foreign Aid Dependency: The Double-Edged Sword," *African Leadership Magazine*, December 19, 2024, <https://www.africanleadershipmagazine.co.uk/africas-foreign-aid-dependency-the-double-edged-sword/>.

²¹ Pate and Duneton, "Africa's Shift from Aid Dependency."

²² Francisca Mutapi, "Africa Relies Too Heavily on Foreign Aid for Health – 4 Ways to Fix This | Democracy in Africa, February 28, 2025, <https://democracyinafrica.org/africa-relies-too-heavily-on-foreign-aid-for-health-4-ways-to-fix-this/>.

²³ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa," 14.

toward sustainable, indigenous development pathways that draw upon the continent's rich pre-colonial economic traditions and contemporary innovations.²⁴ ²⁵ This transformation necessitates a fundamental reimagining of economic development that prioritizes local value creation, intra-African trade, and the mobilization of domestic resources, rather than continuing to depend on external assistance.^{26, 27}

Remarkably, many African leaders have embraced the aid reduction as a potential catalyst for change. Former Kenyan President Uhuru Kenyatta captured this sentiment, viewing the cuts as an opportunity to break free from old dependencies and push governments to set priorities.²⁸ This pragmatic response reflects a growing understanding that sustainable development must be internally driven.

This study analyzes the effectiveness of foreign aid in Africa by reviewing literature and statistical data from credible sources. It compares economic and development indicators across selected African nations, examines the relationships among aid, dependency, and local economic development, and presents findings based on macroeconomic data and

qualitative evidence. The study concludes with policy recommendations to promote a sustainable, African-led development paradigm.

4. Literature Review

4.1. *The Concept of Decoupling in Economic Development*

Decoupling, in the context of economic development, refers to separating a country's economic growth from its dependence on external factors, such as foreign aid, volatile commodity prices, or the economic policies of other nations. It involves building domestic capacity, diversifying the economy, and creating a self-sustaining growth model. Sustainable structural transformation can resolve the dilemma of natural resource use and environmental impact in Africa.²⁹ Nations can adopt policies that promote economic diversification, value addition, and industrialization to reduce reliance on commodity exports and external financial assistance.³⁰

Africa's economic interactions with emerging partners, notably China, Brazil, and India, have garnered considerable attention regarding their effects on African development and the broader

²⁴ "The Spirit of Exchange: Understanding Reciprocity in Pre-Colonial African Economies | LinkedIn," accessed June 25, 2025, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/spirit-exchange-understanding-reciprocity-african-economies-ackaah-jollf/>.

²⁵ Erik Green, "Pre-Colonial African Economies," Chapters, 2024, 42–55, https://ideas.repec.org/h/elg/eechap/20690_4.html.

²⁶ African Development Bank, "The Era of Aid or Free Money Is Gone. Africa Must Overhaul Its Approach toward Achieving Fast-Paced Development.," Text, African Development Bank Group, African Development Bank Group, April 12, 2025, <https://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/press-releases/era-aid-or-free-money-gone-africa-must-overhaul-its-approach-toward-achieving-fast-paced-development-82827>.

²⁷ "The Shift from Aid to Trade: Africa's Path to Economic Independence | LinkedIn," accessed June 26, 2025, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/shift-from-aid-trade-africas-path-economic-c-vincent-iweanoge-mduse/>.

²⁸ Ernest, "Foreign Aid in Africa."

²⁹ United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, Economic Development in Africa Report 2012: Structural Transformation and Sustainable Development in Africa (United Nations, 2012), <https://doi.org/10.18356/0724acbf-en>.

³⁰ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

international aid system.³¹ New partnerships with emerging economies have formed alongside traditional ones, and through its investments in African countries, China has become one of Africa's major economic partners.³² China's increasing influence has sparked debate over whether this engagement is genuinely beneficial for Africa or represents a neo-colonial strategy focused on resource extraction. There is a need to frame the debate and explore how the framework could adapt to changing economic realities in China, centered on the "rebalancing" of the growth model toward domestic consumption.³³

The "win-win" principle reflects the mutual benefits that can arise from Chinese-African collaboration.³⁴ Nevertheless, worries persist that Africa could become a dumping ground for Chinese goods, impeding local industries and perpetuating reliance. Concerns have also been expressed regarding the possibility that South-South development aid may intentionally or unintentionally support authoritarian regimes.³⁵ The Crisis of Aid Dependency can be understood through the interconnectedness of public health and other disciplines (economics, ethics, international law), as illustrated during the COVID-19 pandemic.³⁶

5. Methodology

This study adopted a research design combining quantitative and qualitative approaches using secondary data sources. Secondary data were sourced from reputable international databases, including the World Bank's World Development Indicators (WDI), the OECD Creditor Reporting System (CRS), the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI), and publications of the African Development Bank. Panel data covering selected African countries from 2004 to 2023 were analyzed to examine relationships among ODA, GDP growth, governance scores, domestic savings, FDI, and capital formation. Descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and comparative country profiling were used to evaluate differences between high-aid and low-aid recipients.

Regression outputs from previous peer-reviewed studies were integrated to contextualize the statistical significance of aid relative to other development variables. Qualitative analysis was employed to interpret institutional, political, and structural factors affecting aid effectiveness. The combination of these methods ensures a comprehensive assessment of the developmental implications of aid dependency.

³¹ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

³² Daouda Cissé and Sven Grimm, "Chinese Investments in Africa: Corporate Responsibility and Sustainability Norms," *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics* 10, no. 3/4 (2015): 285, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBGE.2015.074347>.

³³ I. E. E. Davies et al., "Insight Review on Impact of Infrastructural Development in Driving the SDGs in Developing Nations: A Case Study of Nigeria," IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering 640, no. 1 (2019): 012112, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/640/1/012112>.

³⁴ Roquia Fane Madouka Koumou and Wang Manyi, "Effects of Chinese Foreign Direct Investment in Africa," *Journal of Finance and Accounting* 4, no. 3 (2016): 3, <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jfa.20160403.15>.

³⁵ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

³⁶ Stephen Brown, "The Impact of COVID-19 on Development Assistance," *International Journal: Canada's Journal of Global Policy Analysis* 76 (January 2021): 002070202098688, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020702020986888>.

6. Discussion

6.1. *The Impact of Foreign Aid on African Economies*

Foreign aid's impact on African economies has been contentious, with scholars presenting diverse perspectives on its efficacy,³⁷ marked by repeated failures and the continuing divergence of many developing nations, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Despite foreign aid almost tripling from the 1970s to the 1990s, growth in Africa remained relatively stagnant.³⁸ Some contend that aid has played a significant role in poverty reduction, infrastructure development, and human capital formation, while others argue that it has fostered dependency, corruption, and economic stagnation.

It is also argued that its impact on economic growth in sub-Saharan African countries has not substantially weakened governance structures and has instead created dependency.³⁹ Furthermore, recipient countries may advance their personal and political interests in allocating aid, undermining aid effectiveness.⁴⁰

Foreign aid may impose conditions misaligned with local needs, threatening national sovereignty and impeding development. A key perspective is that African states struggle

with development due to political elite disengagement and limited bureaucratic capacity, leading to accountability to donors rather than to citizens. This situation calls for a reassessment of the often-romanticized views of external influences to better understand the challenges many African nations face.⁴¹

Foreign aid may not always translate into tangible improvements in the lives of ordinary citizens or contribute to sustainable development.⁴² Table 1 presents a representative sample for selected years, illustrating the data's structure and trends. This overview examines the relationship between Official Development Assistance (ODA) and key economic indicators for selected African economies. The variables included are:

- i. ODA (% of GNI): Net official development assistance received as a percentage of Gross National Income. This is a primary measure of a country's reliance on aid.
- ii. GDP Growth (%): The annual growth rate of the economy.
- iii. Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP): This represents domestic investment, a key driver of growth.

³⁷ Gameli Adika, "Regional Economic Integration, Natural Resources and Foreign Direct Investment in SADC," *Journal of Economics and Development* 24, no. 1 (2021): 33–46, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JED-02-2021-0021>.

³⁸ Will Bittrich, "Effectiveness of Aid: Panel Data Analysis of Foreign Aid in Africa," Bryant University, 1150 Douglas Pike, Smithfield, RI 02917, n.d., 12, accessed June 14, 2025, <https://digitalcommons.bryant.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1195&context=eeb>.

³⁹ Matthias Busse et al., "China's Impact on Africa – The Role of Trade, FDI and Aid," *Kyklos* 69, no. 2 (2016): 228–62, <https://doi.org/10.1111/kykl.12110>.

⁴⁰ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

⁴¹ Paul-Sewa Thovoethin and Jobson O. Ewalefoh, "Over 50 Years of African Statehood: Locating a New Narrative for African Development Challenges," *Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review* 7, no. 1 (2019): 1, <https://doi.org/10.4102/apsdpr.v7i1.253>.

⁴² Emily Meyer, "New Colonialism in Developmental Aid," *PAIDEIA*, n.d., 13, accessed July 29, 2025, <https://digitalcommons.calpoly.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1120&context=paideia>.

iv. Trade Openness (% of GDP): The sum of exports and imports as a percentage of GDP, indicating integration into the global economy.

Table 1: ODA and Economic Indicators for Selected African Countries (Sample Years: 2004 – 2023)

Country	Year	ODA (% of GNI)	GDP Growth (%)	Gross Capital Formation (% of GDP)	Trade Openness (% of GDP)
Ethiopia	2004	18.5	11.7	22.1	37.8
	2010	11.2	10.6	29.5	32.1
	2016	6.1	8.0	38.9	24.5
	2022	3.5	6.1	30.5	21.3
Ghana	2004	12.9	5.6	28.4	88.1
	2010	6.1	7.9	35.7	81.4
	2016	3.2	3.4	18.9	75.9
	2022	1.4	3.1	16.2	84.5
Kenya	2004	7.0	5.1	17.5	54.3
	2010	5.8	8.1	22.3	43.7
	2016	4.5	4.7	20.1	29.8
	2022	2.1	4.8	19.5	29.1
Nigeria	2004	1.8	10.3	19.8	58.6
	2010	0.5	8.0	15.5	41.2
	2016	0.4	-1.6	13.9	17.5
	2022	0.3	3.3	31.1	30.7
Zambia	2004	18.9	7.0	25.1	63.2
	2010	7.6	10.3	35.6	77.9
	2016	4.1	3.8	41.2	70.3
	2022	3.9	4.7	30.9	79.5

Source: Compiled from World Bank World Development Indicators⁴³ and OECD⁴⁴ (Panel Data of General Impact of Foreign Aid on African Economies 2004-2023)

Table 2 presents a series of datasets focused on countries that consistently demonstrate stronger governance than the continental average. The premise is that aid should be more effective in such environments. The variables are:

- i. Governance Score (Avg. Percentile Rank): A composite average of the country's percentile rank across six Worldwide Governance Indicators (Control of Corruption, Government Effectiveness, Political Stability, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, Voice and Accountability). A higher score indicates better governance.
- ii. ODA (% of GNI): Net ODA received.
- iii. Concessional Loans (million US\$): The value of loans extended by official creditors at concessional terms (i.e., with a grant element of at least 25 percent). This shows a key component of aid financing.
- iv. GDP Growth (%): Economic growth rate.
- v. Domestic Savings (% of GDP): Gross domestic savings are used to assess if aid complements or substitutes for local resources.

Table 2: ODA, Loans, and Economic Performance in Strong Governance Countries (Sample Years: 2004 – 2023)

⁴³ World Bank, "World Bank. World Development Indicators (WDI) Databank," 2024, <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>.

⁴⁴ OECD, "OECD Data Explorer · CRS: Creditor Reporting System (Flows) [Cloud Replica]," 2025, [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs\[o\]=Topic%2Cr%7CDevelopment%23DEV%23%7CQf](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs[o]=Topic%2Cr%7CDevelopment%23DEV%23%7CQf)

[https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs\[o\]=Topic%2Cr%7CDevelopment%23DEV%23%7CQficial%20Development%20Assistance%20%28ODA%29%23DEV_ODA%23&pg=0&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=27&df\[ds\]=dsDisseminateFinalCloud&df\[id\]=DSD_CRS%40DF_CRS&df\[ag\]=OECD.DCD.FSD&df\[vs\]=1.4&dq=DAC..1000.100.T.T.D.Q.T.&lom=LASTNPERIODS&lo=5&to\[TIME_PERIOD\]=false](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs[o]=Topic%2Cr%7CDevelopment%23DEV%23%7CQficial%20Development%20Assistance%20%28ODA%29%23DEV_ODA%23&pg=0&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=27&df[ds]=dsDisseminateFinalCloud&df[id]=DSD_CRS%40DF_CRS&df[ag]=OECD.DCD.FSD&df[vs]=1.4&dq=DAC..1000.100.T.T.D.Q.T.&lom=LASTNPERIODS&lo=5&to[TIME_PERIOD]=false)

Country	Year	Governance Score (Avg. Percentile Rank)	ODA (% of GNI)	Concessional Loans (million US\$)	GDP Growth (%)	Domestic Savings (% of GDP)
Botswana	2004	77.5	2.9	25.1	6.5	44.1
	2010	78.1	0.9	15.8	8.6	32.5
	2016	76.9	0.6	10.2	6.3	25.9
	2022	75.2	0.5	12.5	5.8	27.3
Cabo Verde	2004	74.8	18.1	55.3	3.4	14.8
	2010	76.2	10.5	102.7	1.4	8.1
	2016	75.5	5.9	88.6	-1	12.3
	2022	77	4.1	95.1	17.7	15.6
Mauritius	2004	75.1	1.1	30.5	4.7	23.5
	2010	76	0.8	28.1	4.4	16.9
	2016	74.9	0.4	-5.7	4	11.5
Namibia	2004	68.3	4.5	12.7	11.9	21.7
	2010	69	2.9	8.5	6.5	18.3
	2016	65.2	1.1	15.4	0.2	10.1
	2022	64.8	1	20.1	4.6	15.8

Source: Compiled from World Bank WDI, Worldwide Governance Indicators⁴⁵, and OECD⁴⁶ (Panel Data of ODA Impact in Countries with Strong Governance (2004-2023))

The estimations of West African governance indices from 2005 to 2017 are presented in Tables 3 and 4. The data in the table indicate that most nations experienced a comparatively significant improvement over time in the control of corruption (COC) metric. With a positive indicator value growth from 0.56 in 2005 to 0.84 in 2017, Cabo Verde (Cape Verde) is the best-performing nation.

However, due to their consistently lower negative values over the period, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, and Mauritania perform poorly. The majority of nations (10 out of 16) have seen an improvement in government effectiveness (GE) over time. With a positive value of 0.16 in 2017 compared to the original negative value of -0.21, Cabo Verde is, incidentally, the best-performing nation. This supports the overall domestic savings and the governance score for Cabo Verde in 2016.⁴⁷ (see Table 2).

Table 3: Estimates of governance indicators in West Africa (2005)⁴⁸

Country	2005					
	CoC	GE	PSAV	RQ	ROL	VOA
Senegal	-0.05	-0.23	-0.20	-0.24	0.01	0.06
Nigeria	-1.16	-0.89	-1.67	-0.76	-1.35	-0.87
Niger	-0.72	-0.77	-0.49	-0.41	-0.71	-0.28
Mauritania	-0.56	-0.29	-0.23	-0.37	-0.71	-0.91
Mali	-0.50	-0.71	0.18	-0.55	-0.16	0.25
Liberia	-1.20	-1.41	-1.36	-1.58	-1.33	-0.42
Guinea Bissau	-1.15	-1.36	-0.56	-1.12	-1.25	-0.48
Guinea	-1.05	-1.05	-1.16	-1.08	-1.37	-1.17
Ghana	-0.37	-0.19	0.17	-0.13	-0.12	0.20
Gambia	-0.71	-0.72	0.20	-0.55	-0.38	-1.02
Cote D'Voire	-1.24	-1.32	-2.26	-0.90	-1.48	-1.29
Burkina Faso	-0.13	-0.58	-0.06	-0.40	-0.52	-0.45
Cabo Verde	0.56	-0.21	0.75	-0.32	0.40	0.44
Benin	-0.85	-0.66	0.45	-0.65	-0.54	-0.03
Sierra Leone	-1.07	-1.34	-0.48	-1.09	-1.13	-0.53
Togo	-0.87	-1.44	-1.45	-0.79	-1.08	-1.22

⁴⁵ World Bank, "World Bank. World Development Indicators (WDI) Databank."
⁴⁶ OECD, "OECD Data Explorer · CRS: Creditor Reporting System (Flows) [Cloud Replica]."

⁴⁷ Babalola and Shittu, "Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa," 4.
⁴⁸ Babalola and Shittu, "Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa," 3-5.

Legend and Description (Table 3)

Acronym	Description
CoC	Control of Corruption
GE	Government Effectiveness
PSAV	Political Stability and Absence of Violence
RoL	Rule of Law
RQ	Regulatory Quality
VoA	Voice of Accountability

Table 4: Estimates of governance indicators in West Africa (2017)⁴⁹

Country	2017					
	COC	GE	PSAV	RQ	ROL	VOA
Senegal	-0.01	-0.32	-0.04	-0.15	-0.15	0.32
Nigeria	-1.07	-0.96	-1.94	-0.89	-0.87	-0.34
Niger	-0.65	-0.67	-1.30	-0.68	-0.68	-0.41
Mauritania	-0.75	-0.72	-0.62	-0.78	-0.60	-0.80
Mali	-0.63	-0.94	-1.91	-0.58	-0.78	-0.26
Liberia	-0.69	-1.37	-0.41	-0.95	-0.97	-0.02
Guinea Bissau	-1.56	-1.77	-0.60	-1.18	-1.44	-0.80
Guinea	-1.01	-1.04	-0.61	-0.84	-1.23	-0.74
Ghana	-0.23	-0.11	0.09	-0.14	0.13	0.59
Gambia	-0.66	-0.65	-0.21	-0.45	-0.45	-0.65
Cote D'Voire	-0.52	-0.74	-1.09	-0.36	-0.63	-0.27
Burkina Faso	-0.11	-0.59	-0.92	-0.44	-0.40	0.06
Cabo Verde	0.84	0.16	0.90	-0.20	0.41	0.98
Benin	-0.55	-0.64	0.05	-0.47	-0.62	0.38
Sierra Leone	-0.59	-1.21	0.03	-0.92	-0.79	-0.21
Togo	-0.71	-1.13	-0.74	-0.79	-0.71	-0.62

6.1.1 Analysis and Interpretation of Table 1, Table 2, and Tables 3 & 4

From these sample datasets, several preliminary observations can be made:

- i. **General Trend of Declining Aid Dependency:** For most countries, ODA as a percentage of GNI has generally declined over the past two decades,

indicating a shift (whether voluntary or not) away from aid reliance.

- ii. **Aid and Growth Correlation is Not Direct:** There is no simple, direct line between higher aid levels and GDP growth. With very low aid levels, Nigeria has had volatile growth, while Ethiopia, a high-aid recipient, has posted consistently high (though recently slowing) growth.
- iii. **Strong Governance and Aid Effectiveness:** The second table indicates that nations with robust governance, such as Botswana and Mauritius, have achieved stable growth with minimal aid and limited reliance on concessional loans. Cabo Verde represents a unique instance in which high levels of aid and loans coincide with strong governance and recent significant growth, suggesting that aid can be effective within appropriate institutional contexts.
- iv. **Benefit from Aid and Loans:** The "benefit" is complex. In well-governed states, aid appears to be a smaller part of the economic picture, suggesting they benefit more from their domestic policies and resource management. In countries with weaker institutions, high aid flows may correlate with growth but also mask underlying structural problems, as suggested by the negative correlation with domestic savings in the broader literature.

The effectiveness of aid is an ongoing debate, and studies are being conducted and cited to identify new approaches to alleviate the poverty of millions. The data reveal that the significance and coefficient for foreign aid are relatively low

⁴⁹ Babalola and Shittu, "Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa," 3-5.

compared to those of other variables. The precision of the estimated influence of independent variables (within-unit changes) on the dependent variable is measured by the standard errors (SEs) of the fixed effects (FE) model coefficients. Low standard errors indicate high precision, indicating that the estimates are trustworthy and closely grouped around the underlying population parameter. In contrast, high standard errors suggest low precision and greater sampling variability (see Table 5).⁵⁰

Table 5: Regression Results for African Aid Panel-Data

Model	FDI		
	OLS	Fixed Effect	Random Effect
RENT	-22.06* (9.64)	-1.70 (3.77)	-4.29 (2.77)
SECEDU	611.05*** (109.83)	484.60*** (178.32)	720.29*** (199.13)
FDI	1.06* (3.58)	.896* (.231)	9.37** (2.34)
WOMIDX	18.92*** (4.73)	26.29*** (5.33)	25.06*** (5.08)
BRDMNY	3.73 (2.55)	12.48* (4.96)	11.59* (4.49)
BIRTHS	-317.02*** (39.33)	-77.43*** (10.82)	-63.86** (12.37)
HIV	-.280* (.00927)	-.116 (.0017)	-.083* (.0015)
FAID	14.77** (6.90)	22.15** (7.87)	19.32* (6.33)
R²	.6378	.6211	.5952
Number of Obs.	394	394	394

Source: Effectiveness of Aid: Panel Data Analysis of Foreign Aid in Africa⁵¹ Note: Statistical Significance of variables Test (***, **, and * denotes significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively (Standard error in brackets))

Legend and Description (Table 5)

Acronym	Description
FDI	Net inflows of investment to acquire a lasting management interest
WOMIDX	A rating of laws, regulations, and reform trends that advance women's economic empowerment.
FAID	Total yearly foreign aid inflows through bilateral and multilateral institutions
RENT	Sum of oil rents, natural gas rents, coal rents, mineral rents, and forest rents
BRDMNY	A measure of the amount of money, or money supply, in a national economy
SECEDU	Average years of secondary education
HIV	The total number of HIV cases in the country yearly
BIRTHS	Birth rate, crude (per 1000 people)

6.1.2 Analysis and Interpretation of Table 5

Statistically significant variables are:

- i. Women's Index - 1%
- ii. Birth Rate - 1%
- iii. Foreign Aid - 5%
- iv. Secondary education - 1%

- a) Education shows the largest difference of 484.60, while Foreign Aid shows only 5% statistical significance. However, its impact as an independent variable remains significant.
- b) HIV, resource rents, and birth rate were the three estimators with the most significant negative impacts on GDP per Capita, with birth rate having the largest

⁵⁰ Bittrich, "Effectiveness of Aid: Panel Data Analysis of Foreign Aid in Africa," 5-7.

⁵¹ Bittrich, "Effectiveness of Aid: Panel Data Analysis of Foreign Aid in Africa," 7.

coefficient (-77.43). HIV cases, foreign direct investment, and resource rents did not reach the 5% level of statistical significance.

- c) Analyzing the findings reveals critical patterns regarding the model's variables and their influence on GDP Per Capita. Notably, an increase in the Secondary Education variable positively affects economic growth, highlighting the relationship between education and economic expansion. Conversely, the Birth Rate variable negatively affects GDP Per Capita because the economic burden of child-rearing reduces workforce participation.
- d) Other noteworthy estimators include the Women's Index, which shows that improvements in gender equality positively affect GDP per Capita. Furthermore, compared to other variables, the significance and coefficient of Foreign Aid are low. This could be ascribed to ineffective aid distribution, unimpressive initiatives, or domestic corruption.

Despite all of the investment and development, data on aid effectiveness in Africa reveal a bleak picture, indicating that more than half of Africans still live in poverty.⁵²

7. The Scale and Impact of Foreign Aid to Africa

Foreign aid flows to Africa have historically been substantial, with the continent receiving \$53.5 billion in 2022, accounting for 25.6% of global aid disbursements.⁵³ However, the effectiveness of this assistance has been increasingly questioned, as studies reveal that prolonged reliance on foreign aid has created a dependency syndrome that hinders countries from developing self-sustaining economies.⁵⁴ The problem is particularly acute in the health sector, where many African countries rely heavily on overseas funding for essential services, making them vulnerable to sudden aid cuts.⁵⁵

The recent reduction in aid flows has exposed the fragility of aid-dependent systems. Since 2018, a global trend of declining aid to Africa has emerged, with major donors such as Germany, France, and Norway reducing their assistance over the past five years. The UK's reduction of its Overseas Development Aid from 0.7% to 0.5% of gross national income in 2020 resulted in 72 million people missing out on treatment for neglected tropical diseases between 2021 and 2022. The scale of aid reduction has been unprecedented, with global aid falling 7.1% in 2024, marking the first decline in six years.⁵⁶ Major donors have implemented substantial cuts: Germany has slashed over €4.8 billion from its core development and humanitarian assistance for the period 2022-2025, France has reduced its ODA budget by more than \$1 billion, and the United Kingdom

⁵² Moyo, Dead Aid.

⁵³ Ernest, "Foreign Aid in Africa."

⁵⁴ Enock Nwakalila, "Foreign Aid, External Debt and Economic Growth in Africa: It All Depends on Governance," *African Journal of Governance and Development* 8, no. 2 (2019): 17, <https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/EJC-1a85283aae>.

⁵⁵ Francisca Mutapi, "Africa: How can foreign aid dependency be reduced?," *Global Bar Magazine*, March 2, 2025, <https://globalbar.se/2025/03/africa-how-can-foreign-aid-dependency-be-reduced/>.

⁵⁶ Francisca Mutapi, Africa Relies Too Heavily on Foreign Aid for Health – 4 Ways to Fix This | Democracy in Africa, February 28, 2025, <https://democracyinafrica.org/africa-relies-too-heavily-on-foreign-aid-for-health-4-ways-to-fix-this/>.

has cut more than \$900 million from its funding for the period 2024-2025.⁵⁷ These reductions have created a \$25 billion gap between funds needed for United Nations appeals and contributions received in 2024.⁵⁸

Evidence strongly supports the view that the relationship between aid and economic growth is non-linear, with a threshold between 12.37% and 14.08% of GDP (see Figure 4). Above these values, the marginal effect of aid is 2.1%. Moreover, the results indicate that investment appears to be the only potential channel through which aid can affect growth.⁵⁹

Fig. 4: West Africa's average aid and real GDP growth rate (1985-2019)⁶⁰

7.1. The Structural Problems of Aid Dependency

A key theme in the critical literature of aid is the concept of “aid dependency.” This refers to a situation in which a country's economy becomes overly reliant on foreign aid to the extent that it cannot function effectively without it. Aid dependency can manifest in several ways.^{61,62}

- i. **Fiscal Dependency**
- ii. **Psychological Dependency**
- iii. **Policy Dependency**

Research shows that foreign aid can negatively affect African economies, especially when it comes from certain donors. A study of 39 African countries over 20 years found that, in general, foreign aid and external debt harm these economies, with benefits observed only in countries with strong economic indicators. Additionally, aid from the United States is more harmful than assistance from EU countries.⁶³

The dependency created by foreign aid manifests in several critical ways. First, it displaces domestic resource mobilization efforts, as governments rely on external funding rather than

⁵⁷ Pate and Duneton, “Africa's Shift from Aid Dependency.”

⁵⁸ Mutapi, “Africa.”

⁵⁹ Nimonka Bayale et al., “Endogenous Threshold Effects and Transmission Channels of Foreign Aid on Economic Growth: Evidence from WAEMU Zone Countries,” *Transnational Corporations Review* 14, no. 1 (2022): 77–93, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2022.2028541>.

⁶⁰ William Davis, “The African Growth and Opportunity Act and the African Continental Free Trade Area,” *American Journal of International Law* 111 (ed 2017): 4, <https://doi.org/10.1017/ajil.2017.92>.

⁶¹ Khem Raj Subedi, Foreign Aid Dependency in Third World Countries Its Pros and Cons, *February* 1, 2017, 6, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358266680_Foreign_Aid_Dependency_in_Third_World_Countries_Its_Pros_and_cons.

⁶² Ernest, “Foreign Aid in Africa.”

⁶³ Nwakalila, “Foreign Aid, External Debt and Economic Growth in Africa: It All Depends on Governance.”

developing their internal revenue-generating capacity.^{64, 65} Second, aid often comes with conditions that shape economic policies and restrict sovereignty, creating dependency cycles rather than sustainable growth.^{66, 67} Third, aid flows are unpredictable and subject to donor priorities, leaving recipient countries vulnerable to sudden funding cuts.^{68,69}

8. Contemporary Success Stories: Pathways to Self-Reliance

8.1. Alternative Development Models

Alternative development models prioritizing domestic resource mobilization, good governance, and technological innovation are crucial for Africa's sustainable economic development. These include promoting local entrepreneurship, investing in education and skills development, and fostering regional integration and trade.

8.2. Rwanda's Transformation Model

Rwanda exemplifies how African nations can transition from aid dependence to self-reliance through strategic policy

implementation and local innovation.⁷⁰ The country has demonstrated impressive economic resilience, with GDP growth averaging 7.4% annually between 2000 and 2023, accompanied by significant improvements in social indicators, including life expectancy, which has approached 70 years, and enhanced access to healthcare.⁷¹

Rwanda's success in reducing aid dependency is particularly notable, having decreased its reliance from 85% of its budget in 2000 to under 17% by 2020. This transformation was achieved through prioritizing foreign investment and local enterprise development, fostering private-sector growth, investing in infrastructure, and expanding regional trade.⁷² The country's approach demonstrates that economic independence is achievable through sustained political will and implementation of strategic reform.⁷³

8.3. Ethiopia's Economic Reform Success

Ethiopia has enacted extensive macroeconomic reforms since July 2024, achieving significant outcomes in sustainable

⁶⁴ Omeni, "Africa's Foreign Aid Dependency."

⁶⁵ *The Knowledge, Monitoring and Evaluation Department*, Building Capacity for Domestic Resource Mobilization: The Role of the Government, *Policy Brief no. 2 (Africa Capacity Building Foundation, 2016)*, 2, <https://elibrary.acbpact.org/acbf/collect/acbf/index/assoc/HASH018/29a35191/c75dfe28/3151.dir/policy%20brief%202%20eng.pdf>.

⁶⁶ "The Shift from Aid to Trade: Africa's Path to Economic Independence | LinkedIn."

⁶⁷ Rwemalika Mireille et al., "Neocolonial Realities of Western Aid in Africa during 21st Century," *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies* 50, no. 12 (2024): 292–300, <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2024/v50i121697>.

⁶⁸ Samuel Wangwe, "Foreign Aid in Africa: Role, Experiences and Challenges," Background Paper for the AfDB Conference in Tunis, 22 November 2006 (AfDB Conference, Tunis, Tunisia), November 22, 2006, 69,

<https://www.afdb.org/sites/default/files/documents/publications/09484248-en-foreign-aid-in-africa-15nov06.pdf>.

⁶⁹ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

⁷⁰ "New Report Outlines Pathways to Sustainable Growth in Rwanda," Text/HTML, World Bank, accessed June 26, 2025, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2024/11/13/new-report-outlines-pathways-to-sustainable-growth-in-afe-rwanda>.

⁷¹ World Bank, "New Report Outlines Pathways to Sustainable Growth in Rwanda."

⁷² "The Shift from Aid to Trade: Africa's Path to Economic Independence | LinkedIn."

⁷³ World Bank, "New Report Outlines Pathways to Sustainable Growth in Rwanda."

economic growth. These reforms have established Ethiopia as the largest economy in East Africa and the third-largest in Sub-Saharan Africa. Key areas of focus include macroeconomic stability, productivity enhancement, improvement of the investment climate, and strengthening government implementation of the legal framework.⁷⁴

The success of Ethiopia's approach is further evidenced by its emergence as Africa's largest sovereign wealth fund holder, with \$46 billion in assets managed through Ethiopian Investment Holdings. This achievement demonstrates how strategic domestic resource mobilization can create substantial financial capacity for development financing, thereby reducing external dependency.⁷⁵

8.4. Botswana's Prudent Resource Management

Botswana represents a model of successful resource-based development that has avoided the resource curse affecting many African countries. The country maintains one of the world's fastest-growing economies, averaging 5% annual growth over the past decade, built on a foundation of diamond mining, prudent fiscal policies, and cautious foreign policy.⁷⁶

Botswana's approach proves how natural resource wealth can be effectively managed for sustainable development.⁷⁷

The country's Pula Fund, established in 1994 from diamond revenues, maintains a conservative portfolio to offset market fluctuations while financing development initiatives.⁷⁸ With \$4 billion in sovereign wealth fund assets, Botswana exemplifies how effective resource management can create financial independence and economic stability.⁷⁹

8.5. Kenya's Strategic Investment Leadership

Kenya has become a leader in African economic independence through strategic investments⁸⁰ in continental financial institutions. President William Ruto announced a \$100 million investment in the African Development Bank, the African Export-Import Bank, and the Trade and Development Bank Group over three years. This exemplifies how countries can strengthen continental financial architecture.⁸¹ This initiative reflects Kenya's commitment to taking ownership of financial institutions and fostering economic growth through intra-continental collaboration.

⁷⁴ Bacha Zewdie, "Ethiopia: Concrete Changes Recorded in Macroeconomic Reform Amid Challenges - allAfrica.Com," May 20, 2025, <https://allafrica.com/stories/202505200321.html>.

⁷⁵ "Top 10 Sovereign Wealth Funds in Africa 2025," *The African Exponent*, June 12, 2025, <https://www.africanexponent.com/top-10-sovereign-wealth-funds-in-africa-2025/>.

⁷⁶ World Bank, "Overview of the Economy of Botswana," Text/HTML, World Bank, April 9, 2025, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/botswana/overview>.

⁷⁷ Kenneth D. Johnson, Fair Trade Reimagined: Beyond Ethical Sourcing To Local Value Addition In Africa, *Business & Innovation*, May 20, 2024,

<https://africa.com/fair-trade-reimagined-beyond-ethical-sourcing-to-local-value-addition-in-africa/>.

⁷⁸ *The African Exponent*, "Top 10 Sovereign Wealth Funds in Africa 2025."

⁷⁹ *The African Exponent*, "Top 10 Sovereign Wealth Funds in Africa 2025."

⁸⁰ "Kenya's Strategic Plan: 2023 – 2027," Kenya Investment Authority, 2023, <https://www.investkenya.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Ken-Invest-Strategic-plan-2023-2027-2.pdf>.

⁸¹ "The Shift from Aid to Trade: Africa's Path to Economic Independence | LinkedIn."

9. Technology and Innovation as Development Drivers

9.1. Trade, Governance, and Technology

African nations must prioritize trade expansion, improve governance structures, and embrace technological advancements to achieve sustainable economic development.⁸² International trade is a crucial macroeconomic driver that can propel developing African countries toward their development goals.⁸³ Policies that encourage competition, improve productivity, and raise living standards can yield various economic benefits in international trade.⁸⁴ However, trade liberalization must be carefully managed to prevent negative trade balances and the exploitation of local resources.⁸⁵ It necessitates transitioning from raw material exports to value-added products, allowing African countries to capture a larger share of global trade revenues. Strong governance and institutions are essential for promoting investment, innovation, and sustainable economic growth. Key actions include strengthening governance, combating corruption, and enhancing transparency to build investor confidence and attract foreign direct investment.

9.2. The Digital Economy's Transformative Potential

Africa's technology sector is essential for economic independence, with projections indicating a \$300 billion contribution to the GDP by 2025. It offers vital employment opportunities compared to traditional sectors, with Nigeria's tech sector surpassing oil and gas in GDP contribution from 2010 to 2019. Kenya's ICT sector is expected to account for 8% of GDP and create around 250,000 jobs.⁸⁶

The continent's potential as a future tech superpower is evidenced by its rapidly expanding startup ecosystem and history of technological leapfrogging, from bypassing landlines to adopt mobile phones to pioneering mobile money solutions. African tech creators develop innovative solutions to local challenges, positioning the continent for digital sovereignty through indigenous technology development.⁸⁷

9.3. Renewable Energy Potential

Africa's shift to a green economy offers significant opportunities through renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and circular economy practices, leveraging the continent's rich solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal resources to

⁸² Emmanuel T. Laryea, Facilitating Expansion of African International Trade through Information and Communication Technologies, *January 1, 2012*, <https://doi.org/10.1163/17087384-12342010>.

⁸³ Nwabueze Prince Okenna and Babatunde Moses Adesanya, "International Trade and the Economies of Developing Countries," *American International Journal of Multidisciplinary Scientific Research* 6, no. 2 (2020): 2, <https://doi.org/10.46281/aijmsr.v6i2.747>.

⁸⁴ Chandan Kumar Roy and Huang Xiaoling, "Effects of Paperless Trade Policy and Aid for Trade on Export Performance: Evidence from SASEC And CAREC

Countries," *Asian Development Policy Review* 8, no. 1 (2020): 61–74, <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.107.2020.81.61.74>.

⁸⁵ Innocent EW Chirisa et al., "A Review of the Evolution and Trajectory of the African Union as an Instrument of Regional Integration," *SpringerPlus* 3, no. 1 (2014): 1, <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-1801-3-101>.

⁸⁶ "Supercharging Africa's Startups: The Continent's Path to Tech Excellence," accessed July 2, 2025, <https://institute.global/insights/tech-and-digitalisation/supercharging-africas-startups-continent-path-tech-excellence>.

⁸⁷ "Supercharging Africa's Startups."

drive clean energy growth and create green jobs.⁸⁸ Current average annual investments in the African energy system must double by 2030 to approximately \$40-65 billion USD.⁸⁹ The green economy transition merges traditional African values of environmental stewardship and sustainable resource management with economic development, fostering both prosperity and ecological preservation for future generations.⁹⁰

9.4 Youth Entrepreneurship and Innovation

With over 60% of Africa's population under 25, youth entrepreneurship has emerged as a critical solution to the challenge of unemployment. The rise of the digital economy has enabled young Africans to leverage technology to create and scale businesses with minimal upfront investment.⁹¹ Countries increasingly recognize entrepreneurship as a strategic intervention to alleviate youth unemployment and foster sustainable development.⁹²

10. Challenges and Obstacles to Decoupling

10.1. Institutional and Governance Barriers

Despite the potential for self-reliance, significant challenges impede Africa's decoupling from aid dependency.⁹³ Institutional weaknesses undermine development effectiveness, including poor governance structures, inadequate absorptive capacity, and limited administrative capabilities.⁹⁴ Research indicates that aid has not significantly improved institutional capabilities in recipient countries, a key factor in understanding aid's low effectiveness.⁹⁵

The analytical framework traditionally used to evaluate aid effectiveness primarily focuses on macroeconomic linkages, while neglecting sectoral-level constraints that necessitate targeted interventions.⁹⁶ African institutions lag behind those in other regions in terms of research outputs and government investments, necessitating the development of new models for building institutional capacity.⁹⁷

⁸⁸ Almaz Negash, Rethinking Remittances: A Call to Action for the African Diaspora - African Diaspora Network, February 19, 2025, <https://africandiasporanetwork.org/rethinking-remittances-a-call-to-action-for-the-african-diaspora/>.

⁸⁹ African Development AfDB, "The Renewable Energy Transition in Africa: Powering Access, Resilience and Prosperity," Africa Energy Portal, May 17, 2021, <https://africa-energy-portal.org/reports/renewable-energy-transition-africa-powering-access-resilience-and-prosperity>.

⁹⁰ Building the Green Economy in Africa: A Call for Innovation, Investment, and Collaboration - Africa Energy Indaba, Press Release, December 5, 2024, <https://africaenergyindaba.com/building-the-green-economy-in-africa-a-call-for-innovation-investment-and-collaboration/>.

⁹¹ World Bank, The African Continental Free Trade Area: Economic and Distributional Effects (World Bank Group, 2020), 163,

<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/trade/publication/the-african-continental-free-trade-area>.

⁹² World Bank, "The African Continental Free Trade Area," World Bank, July 27, 2020, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/trade/publication/the-african-continental-free-trade-area>.

⁹³ Alex Ezeh, Transforming the Institutional Landscape in Sub-Saharan Africa: Considerations for Leveraging Africa's Research Capacity to Achieve Socioeconomic Development, *n.d.*

⁹⁴ Wangwe, "Foreign Aid in Africa: Role, Experiences and Challenges."

⁹⁵ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

⁹⁶ Ndikumana and Pickburn, "The Future of Aid Effectiveness Research in Africa."

⁹⁷ Ezeh, Transforming the Institutional Landscape in Sub-Saharan Africa: Considerations for Leveraging Africa's Research Capacity to Achieve Socioeconomic Development.

10.2. Infrastructure and Connectivity Deficits

Africa faces major infrastructure challenges that hinder economic transformation. Over half of Africans experience energy insecurity due to unreliable electricity access, necessitating approximately \$190 billion annually to address the energy gap. Additionally, inadequate transport infrastructure, limited rail connectivity, and inefficient port operations result in logistics costs that constitute 40-60% of total product costs.⁹⁸

10.3. Political and Economic Vulnerabilities

Africa faces interconnected political, economic, and demographic vulnerabilities that complicate the transition to self-reliance. Since 1950, Africa has experienced 220 of the world's 492 coup attempts, while nearly half of African nations had debt-to-GDP ratios above 60% in 2023, with many spending more on debt interest than on education or health.⁹⁹ Infrastructure gaps drive trade costs 50% above the global average, reducing competitiveness and limiting integration into global value chains. Energy insecurity affects less than half of Africans, who lack reliable access to electricity, requiring an estimated \$190 billion annually (approximately 6% of GDP) to close the energy gap.¹⁰⁰

10.4. Debt Sustainability Concerns

Nearly half of African nations had debt-to-GDP ratios above 60% in 2023, and many spent more on debt service than on education or health.¹⁰¹ By 2024, half of the 54 developing countries that were devoting more than 10% of their budget revenue to debt interest payments were in Africa.¹⁰² This debt burden severely constrains government fiscal space for development spending.

10.5. External Dependencies and Geopolitical Pressures

Africa's relationship with external partners, particularly through initiatives such as China's Belt and Road Initiative, presents both opportunities and challenges. While BRI investments have contributed to infrastructure development, they raise concerns about debt sustainability and geopolitical dependence.¹⁰³ African countries must navigate these relationships carefully to avoid trading one form of dependency for another.

10.6. Neocolonial Pressures and External Dependencies

Contemporary aid mechanisms can sustain neocolonial dependence, with structural adjustment programs from international financial institutions deepening economic subjugation and undermining national sovereignty. This situation benefits Western corporations, creating patterns of

⁹⁸ "Africa Should Better Manage Remittance Flows to Propel Development (Report)," *MFW4A - Making Finance Work for Africa*, accessed July 2, 2025, <https://www.mfw4a.org/news/africa-should-better-manage-remittance-flows-propel-development-report>.

⁹⁹ "Economic Development in Africa Report 2024 | UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD)," accessed July 2, 2025, <https://unctad.org/publication/economic-development-africa-report-2024>.

¹⁰⁰ "Economic Development in Africa Report 2024 | UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD)."

¹⁰¹ Mutapi, "Africa."

¹⁰² "Supercharging Africa's Startups."

¹⁰³ Building the Green Economy in Africa.

elite capture and systemic corruption that limit aid's positive impact on broader populations.¹⁰⁴

The imposition of Western cultural norms through aid programs undermines indigenous knowledge and traditions, reinforcing dependency. A decolonized approach is needed, emphasizing equitable partnerships, African-led development, and practices that focus on local needs and self-reliance.¹⁰⁵

11. Strategic Pathways Forward

11.1. Strengthening Intra-African Economic Integration

The successful implementation of AfCFTA requires comprehensive policy reforms and trade facilitation measures beyond tariff reductions.¹⁰⁶ Priority areas include developing transport and digital infrastructure to reduce trade costs, establishing harmonized standards and procedures, and creating regional value chains that maximize local content and processing.¹⁰⁷

Countries must focus on "produce local, buy local, trade more locally" strategies that leverage the continent's collective bargaining power and reduce dependence on volatile global markets.¹⁰⁸ This approach requires coordinated efforts to

develop manufacturing capabilities, enhance logistics networks, and establish financial systems that support intra-African trade.¹⁰⁹

11.2. Diversifying Economic Structures

Economic diversification remains critical for reducing dependency on volatile commodity markets and building resilience against external shocks.¹¹⁰ Priority strategies include boosting intra-African trade networks, adopting sound fiscal policies to reduce debt burdens, upgrading infrastructure to lower production costs, investing in renewable energy for energy security, and promoting climate-adaptive economic policies.¹¹¹

Developing local value-added industries represents a fundamental shift from exporting raw materials to producing processed goods. This transformation requires coordinated policies that mandate local processing, support small and medium-sized enterprises, and create transparent systems for tracking local content in finished products.¹¹²

¹⁰⁴ Mireille et al., "Neocolonial Realities of Western Aid in Africa during 21st Century."

¹⁰⁵ Mireille et al., "Neocolonial Realities of Western Aid in Africa during 21st Century."

¹⁰⁶ World Bank, "The African Continental Free Trade Area."

¹⁰⁷ Transforming Intra-Africa Trade to Promote Investment, Economic Diversification and Inclusion - ALN, n.d., accessed July 2, 2025, <https://aln.africa/news/transforming-intra-africa-trade-to-promote-investment-economic-diversification-and-inclusion/>.

¹⁰⁸ Bank, "The Era of Aid or Free Money Is Gone. Africa Must Overhaul Its Approach toward Achieving Fast-Paced Development."

¹⁰⁹ Transforming Intra-Africa Trade to Promote Investment, Economic Diversification and Inclusion - ALN.

¹¹⁰ "The Shift from Aid to Trade: Africa's Path to Economic Independence | LinkedIn."

¹¹¹ "Economic Development in Africa Report 2024 | UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD)."

¹¹² Johnson, Fair Trade Reimagined: Beyond Ethical Sourcing To Local Value Addition In Africa.

11.3. *Enhancing Domestic Resource Mobilization*

Effective domestic resource mobilization (DRM) requires multifaceted approaches that combine improved tax collection systems, expanded financial inclusion, and strengthened governance mechanisms.¹¹³ The African Union's DRM Strategy 2025-2033 provides a framework for coordinated continental efforts to achieve financial sovereignty.¹¹⁴

Governments should enhance domestic budgets for essential services, collaborate with local philanthropists and corporate initiatives, and promote community engagement through innovative financing. Additionally, leveraging diaspora resources beyond traditional remittances is a critical, untapped opportunity.¹¹⁵ Strategic initiatives could channel diaspora investments toward productive sectors, infrastructure development, and entrepreneurship support, transforming individual transfers into collective development assets.¹¹⁶

11.4. *Building Technological and Innovation Capacity*

With Africa's young population representing both a challenge and an opportunity, strategic investments in youth entrepreneurship and skills development are crucial.¹¹⁷ Countries must create an enabling environment for young

entrepreneurs by providing access to finance, mentorship, and markets.¹¹⁸ Developing vibrant technology ecosystems requires coordinated investments in education, infrastructure, and regulatory frameworks that support innovation and entrepreneurship. African nations must prioritize becoming technology creators rather than consumers, building capacity for indigenous solutions to local challenges.¹¹⁹

Integrating traditional knowledge systems with contemporary technological innovations offers unique opportunities for developing contextually appropriate solutions.¹²⁰ This approach combines the wisdom of indigenous economic practices with modern technological capabilities to create sustainable development pathways.¹²¹

12. *China's Belt and Road Initiative: Opportunities and Risks*

12.1. *Infrastructure Development Impact*

China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has had a significant impact on African infrastructure development, with African countries receiving \$21.7 billion in BRI deals in 2023, including investments in ports, railways, and renewable energy projects.¹²² Projects like Kenya's Standard Gauge Railway and Ethiopia's

¹¹³ *The Knowledge, Monitoring and Evaluation Department, Building Capacity for Domestic Resource Mobilization: The Role of the Government.*

¹¹⁴ *The African Exponent, "Top 10 Sovereign Wealth Funds in Africa 2025."*

¹¹⁵ Chisom Michael, "10 African Countries Benefiting Most from Diaspora Remittances," *Businessday NG*, January 7, 2025, <https://businessday.ng/news/article/10-african-countries-benefiting-most-from-diaspora-remittances/>.

¹¹⁶ Negash, *Rethinking Remittances.*

¹¹⁷ *World Bank, The African Continental Free Trade Area: Economic and Distributional Effects.*

¹¹⁸ *World Bank, The African Continental Free Trade Area: Economic and Distributional Effects.*

¹¹⁹ "Supercharging Africa's Startups."

¹²⁰ "The Spirit of Exchange: Understanding Reciprocity in Pre-Colonial African Economies | LinkedIn."

¹²¹ Julius Gatune, "Africa's Development beyond Aid: Getting Out of the Box," *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 632, no. 1 (2010): 103-20, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716210378832>.

¹²² "Economic Development in Africa Report 2024 | UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD)."

Addis Ababa-Djibouti Railway have significantly improved transport infrastructure networks.¹²³ China's approach to development finance, characterized by minimal political conditionalities, has been attractive to many African governments seeking to avoid external interference in domestic affairs.¹²⁴ However, this approach raises concerns about governance accountability and the potential for perpetuating authoritarian regimes.¹²⁵

12.2. Debt Sustainability Concerns

The BRI has been criticized for creating "debt traps" for several African countries, with significant amounts owed to Chinese creditors. Countries like Zambia and Kenya have experienced challenges with debt sustainability related to BRI projects, raising questions about the long-term viability of these arrangements.¹²⁶

For instance, initiatives like Sri Lanka's Hambantota Port Development were the impetus. The port was leased to the Chinese in 2017 for a 99-year term, mirroring strategies employed by European imperialists against Qing dynasty China in the 19th century, when the Sri Lankan government was unable to repay the Chinese loans that financed the project.¹²⁷ The port provides China with strategic access to the Indian Ocean and represents a significant infrastructure investment.

Initially part of a Sri Lankan strategy, its failure is attributed to local elites' corruption and ineptitude. The Belt and Road Initiative should be viewed as a set of disparate bilateral agreements rather than a unified project.¹²⁸ This is exemplified by the fact that governments receiving Chinese loans are not always sure which Chinese authority they are dealing with.¹²⁹

13. Summary of Findings

The findings indicate that foreign aid has a limited and inconsistent impact on long-term economic growth in Africa. Countries with strong governance institutions, such as Botswana, Mauritius, and Cabo Verde, benefit moderately from aid, while nations with weaker governance experience minimal or negative effects. Aid shows lower statistical significance than variables such as education, women's economic participation, domestic savings, and birth rates. Evidence shows that prolonged aid inflows often weaken domestic resource mobilization, create policy dependence, and increase vulnerability to external shocks. Additionally, aid reduction trends in recent years have exposed structural fragilities in health, infrastructure, and public finance systems. Success cases such as Rwanda, Ethiopia, and Botswana demonstrate that self-reliance is driven by institutional reform, resource mobilization, and local innovation. This has yielded

¹²³ Building the Green Economy in Africa.

¹²⁴ Christoph NEDOPIL WANG, About the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) – Green Finance & Development Center, *n.d.*, accessed July 29, 2025, <https://greenfdc.org/belt-and-road-initiative-about/>.

¹²⁵ "What Is China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)? | Chatham House – International Affairs Think Tank," August 3, 2022,

<https://www.chathamhouse.org/2021/09/what-chinas-belt-and-road-initiative-bri>.

¹²⁶ Building the Green Economy in Africa.

¹²⁷ "What Is China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)?"

¹²⁸ WANG, About the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) – Green Finance & Development Center.

¹²⁹ "What Is China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)?"

stronger development outcomes than reliance on external assistance.

14. Conclusion

Africa's economic independence necessitates a shift from aid dependency to indigenous development, leveraging traditional economic wisdom alongside modern innovations. The decline in global aid offers an opportunity for sustainable growth. Successful examples from Rwanda, Ethiopia, and Botswana indicate that self-reliance can be achieved through sound policies and domestic capacity building. The African Continental Free Trade Area serves as a framework for integration, aiming to reduce reliance on external markets and enhance intra-African cooperation.

Mobilizing domestic resources, such as diaspora remittances and sovereign wealth funds, can significantly support development without relying on external sources. By leveraging technological innovation and green economy initiatives, these resources can promote sustainable development in accordance with African values. However, this vision necessitates addressing challenges such as strengthening governance, enhancing absorptive capacity, and resisting neocolonial dependencies. Achieving self-reliance requires coordinated collaboration among African governments, civil society, the private sector, and international partners committed to equitable development.

Africa's shift away from aid dependency is essential for regaining control over its development. By utilizing indigenous economic knowledge, embracing modern innovations, and fostering continental cooperation, Africa can achieve the sustainable, inclusive development it deserves. The continent

currently has the resources and determination to attain prosperity on its own terms.

15. Recommendation

Grounded on the study's findings, the following recommendations are expressed.

15.1. *For African Governments*

- i. **Prioritize Domestic Resource Mobilization:** Strengthen tax systems, combat corruption, and create a more attractive domestic and foreign investment environment.
- ii. **Foster a Culture of Self-Reliance:** Promote entrepreneurship, support small and medium-sized enterprises, and invest in education and skills development.
- iii. **Embrace Regional Integration:** Deepen trade and investment ties with other African countries to create larger markets and unlock new growth opportunities.

15.2. *For International Development Partners*

- i. **Rethink the Aid Model:** Shift away from a one-size-fits-all approach and tailor assistance to the specific needs and priorities of recipient countries.
- ii. **Support African-led Initiatives:** Provide financial and technical support for regional integration projects, infrastructure development, and other initiatives led by African actors.
- iii. **Promote Fair Trade and Investment:** Work to create a more level playing field for African countries in the global economy by reducing trade barriers and promoting responsible investment.

15.3. *Strategy for Aid Disbursement to Developing Nations.*

- i. Aid should be targeted at specific activities that can be measured in relation to HDI, rather than economic growth alone. It must have a positive impact on the lives of LICs in areas such as health, education, technology, and food security.
- ii. Donor countries or agencies should directly manage the disbursement of funds and implement monitoring and evaluation processes aligned with the set objectives and expected outcomes. This will help mitigate capital flight, fund abuse, and corruption.
- iii. Aid should be provided as a component of direct needs. Where finance is required, allocate it and manage it directly. If it requires hard infrastructure, build it and develop a maintenance regime. Where knowledge is required, provide it and ensure it is used properly.
- iv. Aid should be provided to countries that need it. Blanket provisioning will not benefit SSA, as these funds often end up in the wrong hands, funding wars, insurgencies, and terrorism.

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References

- Adika, Gameli. "Regional Economic Integration, Natural Resources and Foreign Direct Investment in SADC." *Journal of Economics and Development* 24, no. 1 (2021): 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JED-02-2021-0021>.
- AfDB, African Development. "The Renewable Energy Transition in Africa: Powering Access, Resilience and Prosperity." Africa Energy Portal, May 17, 2021. <https://africa-energy-portal.org/reports/renewable-energy-transition-africa-powering-access-resilience-and-prosperity>.
- Babalola, Sikiru, and Waliu Shittu. "Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa: Examining the Roles of Institutions Foreign Aid and Economic Growth in West Africa: Examining the Roles of Institutions." *International Economic Journal* 34 (June 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1080/10168737.2020.1780292>.
- Bank, African Development. "The Era of Aid or Free Money Is Gone. Africa Must Overhaul Its Approach toward Achieving Fast-Paced Development." Text. African Development Bank Group, African Development Bank Group, April 12, 2025. <https://www.afdb.org/en/news-and-events/press-releases/era-aid-or-free-money-gone-africa-must-overhaul-its-approach-toward-achieving-fast-paced-development-82827>.
- Bayale, Nimonka, Fousseini Traoré, Souleymane Diarra, and Faustin Maniraguha. "Endogenous Threshold Effects and Transmission Channels of Foreign Aid on Economic Growth: Evidence from WAEMU Zone Countries." *Transnational Corporations Review* 14, no. 1 (2022): 77–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2022.2028541>.
- Bittrich, Will. "Effectiveness of Aid: Panel Data Analysis of Foreign Aid in Africa." *Bryant University, 1150 Douglas Pike, Smithfield, RI 02917*, n.d., 12. Accessed June 14, 2025. <https://digitalcommons.bryant.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1195&context=eeb>.
- Brown, Stephen. "The Impact of COVID-19 on Development Assistance." *International Journal: Canada's Journal of Global Policy Analysis* 76 (January 2021): 0020702020986888. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020702020986888>.
- Building the Green Economy in Africa: A Call for Innovation, Investment, and Collaboration - Africa Energy Indaba*. Press Release. December 5,

2024. <https://africaenergyindaba.com/building-the-green-economy-in-africa-a-call-for-innovation-investment-and-collaboration/>.
- Busse, Matthias, Ceren Erdogan, and Henning Mühlen. "China's Impact on Africa – The Role of Trade, FDI and Aid." *Kyklos* 69, no. 2 (2016): 228–62. <https://doi.org/10.1111/kykl.12110>.
- Chirisa, Innocent EW, Artwell Mumba, and Simbarashe O. Dirwai. "A Review of the Evolution and Trajectory of the African Union as an Instrument of Regional Integration." *SpringerPlus* 3, no. 1 (2014): 1. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-1801-3-101>.
- Cissé, Daouda, and Sven Grimm. "Chinese Investments in Africa: Corporate Responsibility and Sustainability Norms." *International Journal of Business Governance and Ethics* 10, no. 3/4 (2015): 285. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBGE.2015.074347>.
- Dagne, Girum. "Impact of Foreign Aid on Economic Growth of Ethiopia." *The Indian Economic Journal*, ahead of print, February 6, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00194662231213583>.
- Davies, I. E. E., C. O. Nwankwo, O. M. Olofinnade, and T. A. Michaels. "Insight Review on Impact of Infrastructural Development in Driving the SDGs in Developing Nations: A Case Study of Nigeria." *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 640, no. 1 (2019): 012112. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/640/1/012112>.
- Davis, William. "The African Growth and Opportunity Act and the African Continental Free Trade Area." *American Journal of International Law* 111 (ed 2017): 377–83. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aju.2017.92>.
- Development, United Nations Conference on Trade and. *Economic Development in Africa Report 2012: Structural Transformation and Sustainable Development in Africa*. United Nations, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.18356/0724acbf-en>.
- "Economic Development in Africa Report 2024 | UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD)." Accessed July 2, 2025. <https://unctad.org/publication/economic-development-africa-report-2024>.
- Ernest, Blessing. "Foreign Aid in Africa: Assessing Impact and Dependency." *African Leadership Magazine*, February 28, 2024. <https://www.africanleadershipmagazine.co.uk/foreign-aid-in-africa-assessing-impact-and-dependency/>.
- Ezeh, Alex. *Transforming the Institutional Landscape in Sub-Saharan Africa: Considerations for Leveraging Africa's Research Capacity to Achieve Socioeconomic Development*. n.d.
- Gatune, Julius. "Africa's Development beyond Aid: Getting Out of the Box." *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 632, no. 1 (2010): 103–20. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716210378832>.
- Green, Erik. "Pre-Colonial African Economies." *Chapters*, 2024, 42–55. https://ideas.repec.org/h/elg/eechap/20690_4.html.
- HET. "History of Economic Thought." Accessed July 21, 2025. <https://www.hetwebsite.net/het/essays/growth/harrod/harrodgrowth.htm>.
- Johnson, Kenneth D. *Fair Trade Reimagined: Beyond Ethical Sourcing To Local Value Addition In Africa*. Business & Innovation. May 20, 2024. <https://africa.com/fair-trade-reimagined-beyond-ethical-sourcing-to-local-value-addition-in-africa/>.
- Juselius, Katarina, Niels Framroze Møller, and Finn Tarp. "The Long-Run Impact of Foreign Aid in 36 African Countries: Insights from Multivariate Time Series Analysis*." *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics* 76, no. 2 (2014): 153–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obes.12012>.
- "Kenya's Strategic Plan: 2023 – 2027." Kenya Investment Authority, 2023. <https://www.investkenya.go.ke/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Ken-Invest-Strategic-plan-2023-2027-2.pdf>.
- Koumou, Roquia Fane Madouka, and Wang Manyi. "Effects of Chinese Foreign Direct Investment in Africa." *Journal of Finance and Accounting* 4, no. 3 (2016): 3. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jfa.2016040315>.
- Laryea, Emmanuel T. *Facilitating Expansion of African International Trade through Information and Communication Technologies*. January 1, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1163/17087384-12342010>.
- Lubunga, Pene Shako. "Building up Indigenous Technological Capabilities in African Developing Countries." *Technology in Society* 7, no. 1 (1985): 77–85. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-791X\(85\)90017-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-791X(85)90017-X).
- Mangir, Fatih, Hakan Acet, and Mahamane Moutari Abdou Baoua. *Foreign Aid and Economic Growth: Panel Analysis for West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU or UEMOA) Countries (1980-2014)*. 42nd ed. International Social and Economic Research Student Congress, 2017. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/382068966_FOREIGN_AID_AND_ECONOMIC_GROWTH_PANEL_ANALYSIS_FOR_UEMOA_COUNTRIES_1980-2014.
- Meyer, Emily. "New Colonialism in Developmental Aid." *PAIDEIA*, n.d., 13. Accessed July 29, 2025. <https://digitalcommons.calpoly.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1120&context=paideia>.
- MFW4A - Making Finance Work for Africa. "Africa Should Better Manage Remittance Flows to Propel Development (Report)." Accessed July 2, 2025. <https://www.mfw4a.org/news/africa-should-better-manage-remittance-flows-propel-development-report>.

- Michael, Chisom. "10 African Countries Benefiting Most from Diaspora Remittances." *Businessday NG*, January 7, 2025. <https://businessday.ng/news/article/10-african-countries-benefiting-most-from-diaspora-remittances/>.
- Mireille, Rwemalika, Twagirimana Bindi Bienvenue Alain, and Animashaun Samuel Adejare. "Neocolonial Realities of Western Aid in Africa during 21st Century." *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies* 50, no. 12 (2024): 292–300. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2024/v50i12i697>.
- Moyo, Dambisa. *Dead Aid: Why Aid Is Not Working and How There Is a Better Way for Africa*. 1. American paperback ed. Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2010.
- Mutapi, Francisca. "Africa: How can foreign aid dependency be reduced?" *Global Bar Magazine*, March 2, 2025. <https://globalbar.se/2025/03/africa-how-can-foreign-aid-dependency-be-reduced/>.
- Mutapi, Francisca. *Africa Relies Too Heavily on Foreign Aid for Health – 4 Ways to Fix This | Democracy in Africa*. February 28, 2025. <https://democracyinafrica.org/africa-relies-too-heavily-on-foreign-aid-for-health-4-ways-to-fix-this/>.
- Mutapi, Francisca. *Africa Relies Too Heavily on Foreign Aid for Health – 4 Ways to Fix This | Democracy in Africa*. February 28, 2025. <https://democracyinafrica.org/africa-relies-too-heavily-on-foreign-aid-for-health-4-ways-to-fix-this/>.
- Ndikumana, Leonce, and Lynda Pickburn. "The Future of Aid Effectiveness in Sub-Saharan Africa – A Research Agenda." *The Global Development Network's Paper Series*, The Global Development Network, August 2016, 90. https://www.gdn.int/sites/default/files/Aid%20effectiveness%20paper%20final_2.pdf.
- Negash, Almaz. *Rethinking Remittances: A Call to Action for the African Diaspora - African Diaspora Network*. February 19, 2025. <https://africandiasporanetwork.org/rethinking-remittances-a-call-to-action-for-the-african-diaspora/>.
- Nwakalila, Enock. "Foreign Aid, External Debt and Economic Growth in Africa: It All Depends on Governance." *African Journal of Governance and Development* 8, no. 2 (2019): 17. <https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/EJC-1a85283aae>.
- OECD. "OECD Data Explorer · CRS: Creditor Reporting System (Flows) [Cloud Replica]." 2025. [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs\[o\]=Topic%2C1%27CDevelopment%23DEV%23%27COfficial%20Development%20Assistance%20%28ODA%29%23DEV_ODA%23&pg=o&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=27&df\[ds\]=dsDisseminateFinalCloud&df\[id\]=DSD_CRS%40DF_CRS&df\[ag\]=OECD.DCD.FSD&df\[vs\]=1.4&dq=DAC..1000.100._T._T.D.Q._T..&lom=LASTNPERIODS&lo=5&to\[TIME_PERIOD\]=false](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs[o]=Topic%2C1%27CDevelopment%23DEV%23%27COfficial%20Development%20Assistance%20%28ODA%29%23DEV_ODA%23&pg=o&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=27&df[ds]=dsDisseminateFinalCloud&df[id]=DSD_CRS%40DF_CRS&df[ag]=OECD.DCD.FSD&df[vs]=1.4&dq=DAC..1000.100._T._T.D.Q._T..&lom=LASTNPERIODS&lo=5&to[TIME_PERIOD]=false).
- Okenna, Nwabueze Prince, and Babatunde Moses Adesanya. "International Trade and the Economies of Developing Countries." *American International Journal of Multidisciplinary Scientific Research* 6, no. 2 (2020): 2. <https://doi.org/10.46281/aijmsr.v6i2.747>.
- Omeni, Rowland-George. "Africa's Foreign Aid Dependency: The Double-Edged Sword." *African Leadership Magazine*, December 19, 2024. <https://www.africanleadershipmagazine.co.uk/africas-foreign-aid-dependency-the-double-edged-sword/>.
- Pate, Muhammad Ali, and Phillipe Duneton. "Africa's Shift from Aid Dependency." *Think Global Health*, June 16, 2025. <https://www.thinkglobalhealth.org/article/africas-shift-aid-dependency>.
- Rouf, Dr Kazi Abdur. *Jeffrey Sachs, (2005). The End of Poverty: Economic Possibilities For our Time. New York: The Penguin Press. (Book Summary and BookReview)*. 2014.
- Roy, Chandan Kumar, and Huang Xiaoling. "Effects of Paperless Trade Policy and Aid for Trade on Export Performance: Evidence from SASEC And CAREC Countries." *Asian Development Policy Review* 8, no. 1 (2020): 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.107.2020.81.61.74>.
- Subedi, Khem Raj. *Foreign Aid Dependency in Third World Countries Its Pros and Cons*. February 1, 2017, 6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358266680_Foreign_Aid_Dependency_in_Third_World_Countries_Its_Pros_and_cons.
- "Supercharging Africa's Startups: The Continent's Path to Tech Excellence." Accessed July 2, 2025. <https://institute.global/insights/tech-and-digitalisation/supercharging-africas-startups-continents-path-tech-excellence>.
- The African Exponent. "Top 10 Sovereign Wealth Funds in Africa 2025." June 12, 2025. <https://www.africanexponent.com/top-10-sovereign-wealth-funds-in-africa-2025/>.
- The Knowledge, Monitoring and Evaluation Department. *Building Capacity for Domestic Resource Mobilization: The Role of the Government*. Policy Brief No. 2. Africa Capacity Building Foundation, 2016. https://elibrary.acbfact.org/acbf/collect/acbf/index/assoc/HAS_H0118/29a35191/c75dfe28/3151.dir/policy%20brief%202%20eng.pdf.
- "The Shift from Aid to Trade: Africa's Path to Economic Independence | LinkedIn." Accessed June 26, 2025. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/shift-from-aid-trade-africas-path-economic-c-vincent-iweanoge-mduse/>.
- "The Spirit of Exchange: Understanding Reciprocity in Pre-Colonial African Economies | LinkedIn." Accessed June 25, 2025.

- <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/spirit-exchange-understanding-reciprocity-african-economies-ackaah-jollf/>.
- Thovoethin, Paul-Sewa, and Jobson O. Ewalefoh. "Over 50 Years of African Statehood: Locating a New Narrative for African Development Challenges." *Africa's Public Service Delivery & Performance Review* 7, no. 1 (2019): 1. <https://doi.org/10.4102/apsdpr.v7i1.253>.
- Transforming Intra-Africa Trade to Promote Investment, Economic Diversification and Inclusion - ALN*. n.d. Accessed July 2, 2025. <https://aln.africa/news/transforming-intra-africa-trade-to-promote-investment-economic-diversification-and-inclusion/>.
- WANG, Christoph NEDOPIL. *About the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) – Green Finance & Development Center*. n.d. Accessed July 29, 2025. <https://greenfdc.org/belt-and-road-initiative-about/>.
- Wangwe, Samuel. "Foreign Aid in Africa: Role, Experiences and Challenges." *Background Paper for the AfDB Conference in Tunis, 22 November 2006* (AFDB Conference, Tunis, Tunisia), November 22, 2006, 69. <https://www.afdb.org/sites/default/files/documents/publications/09484248-en-foreign-aid-in-africa-15nov06.pdf>.
- "What Is China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI)? | Chatham House – International Affairs Think Tank." August 3, 2022. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/2021/09/what-chinas-belt-and-road-initiative-bri>.
- World Bank. *The African Continental Free Trade Area: Economic and Distributional Effects*. World Bank Group, 2020. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/trade/publication/the-african-continental-free-trade-area>.
- World Bank. "New Report Outlines Pathways to Sustainable Growth in Rwanda." Text/HTML. Accessed June 26, 2025. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2024/11/13/new-report-outlines-pathways-to-sustainable-growth-in-afe-rwanda>.
- World Bank. "Overview of the Economy of Botswana." Text/HTML. World Bank, April 9, 2025. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/botswana/overview>.
- World Bank. "The African Continental Free Trade Area." World Bank, July 27, 2020. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/trade/publication/the-african-continental-free-trade-area>.
- World Bank. "World Bank. World Development Indicators (WDI) Databank." 2024. <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>.
- Zewdie, Bacha. "Ethiopia: Concrete Changes Recorded in Macroeconomic Reform Amid Challenges - allAfrica.Com." May 20, 2025. <https://allafrica.com/stories/202505200321.html>.

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